

Making Sense of Division: Conceptual Insights for Fractions with Non-Integer Divisors

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Abstract:

This paper presents a novel conceptual framework elucidating the duality between grouping and partitioning in division. Traditionally, grouping focuses on how many complete portions fit within a whole, providing the number of groups formed. In contrast, partitioning emphasizes the size of each group created from the whole, where the divisor represents the number of groups instead. This study explores the implications of dividing by fractions, particularly those less than 1, revealing that partitioning can conceptually accommodate divisions where the divisor represents a fractional group. Specifically, it posits that when dividing a unit by a fraction, the resulting group must encompass the whole, leading to a deeper understanding of the relationship between the divisor and the dividend. Through this dual framework, the paper aims to enhance mathematical comprehension and facilitate an intuitive understanding of numbers.

Introduction:

I was looking into the functioning of the website Polymarket, and its hybrid gambling-shares system caught my attention. To bet on binary events, you purchase shares whose value reflects the probability of that event occurring. Market forces determine the price of shares, comprised between 0 and 1 dollar, just like the probability of an event ranges from 0 to 1. When the time is up, the share will be worth either 0 or 1 dollar.

For a share that costs 60 cents, it is easy to calculate the potential return: we just divide the amount invested, let's say \$1, by 0,6, and obtain 1,66.

For a person who often deals with statistics, percentages, probabilities or financial data, this kind of operation comes naturally, without even thinking about it.

Despite that, if we abstract from the unit of measurement, in this case dollars, and focus solely on the raw numbers, understanding what this operation represents becomes trickier. This realization prompted me to consider how we understand and conceptualize numbers, particularly divisions.

People can intuitively, graphically and conceptually understand what $10/2$ means, or $1/10$, or even $1/1$, but it seems way harder to instinctively get what it means to divide one by a number comprised between 0 and 1.

For example, the result of 1 divided by 2 tells us what number fits within the number one for two times. But what does the result of one divided by 0,6 tell us?

Exploring these types of questions can expand our understanding of numerical concepts. It can shed light on the way individuals process and make sense of numerical information, providing insights into the nature of mathematical cognition.

Moreover, this exploration can significantly benefit learners. By clarifying the conceptual underpinnings of divisions, it is possible to help young students grasp these concepts more intuitively, overcoming misconceptions that can hinder their mathematical development.

Conceptual framework:

Let's start with a straightforward case: $10/2$.

What I do is imagine 10 units of something, and split them into two groups. The result of the division is represented by the number of units inside of each group. I found out that this visual representation is called the partitioning method. It is not the only possible method though.

For some people, the result of 10 divided by 2 may be represented not by the units within each of the two groups, but by the number of groups that are made up of two units each. Instead of making two groups of five units, they make groups of two units, until they run out of units to make groups with. Then they count the resulting number of groups, 5 in this case. This is called the grouping approach.

Others may rely on simply memorizing the basic numerical operations, and as the problems get more complex, they simply break them down into simpler components, until they get to the core operations which they can solve by memory.

To sum up, the partitioning method lets us visualize the number of units in each group, after redistributing the units of the dividend into n groups, where n is the divisor.

The grouping method on the other hand tells us how many groups the size of the divisor can be made with the units of the dividend. Said another way, how many times the divisor fits into the dividend.

The grouping method is a universal way of interpreting the meaning of a division, as it works with any kind of number. It is also the method that is normally taught to kids to help them make sense of divisions. I argue however that it does not offer the same intuitive clarity that the partitioning method does.

The partitioning method on the other hand, although may seem more straightforward, apparently makes sense for integer numbers only. After all, it makes sense to divide 10 into two groups, or even 1 unit into 4 groups. We can even stretch our minds a little bit to understand how 4 can be divided into 1,2 groups. However, the concepts of dividing a number by a value comprised between 0 and 1 seem to make no sense at all from the partitioning perspective; what does it even mean to divide 1 unit into 0,6 groups?

I will present an interpretation of this problem below. To do so, I will analyze four different divisions using both visualization methods -partitioning and grouping- beginning with the most intuitively understandable case and progressing to the one that appears to lack a clear conceptual explanation.

Dividing 10 by 4:

With the **grouping** method, from the 10 units set, we draw units one by one to create groups of 4 units. After creating two groups, only 2 units remain, which is half a normal group. So with the grouping approach, from 10 units we can create 2,5 groups of 4 units each.

With the **partitioning** method, we put 10 marbles on the table and divide them into four groups. We will have to cut two of them in half, and we will have 4 groups of 2,5 marbles each.

Dividing 1 by 4:

With the **grouping** approach, we want to create as many groups of 4 units using the single available unit. The result is 0,25, given that with 1 unit we can only create a quarter of a group of 4 units.

Alternatively, we can think about how many times the four fits into the number 1, which is 0,25 times.

Using the **partitioning** approach, given that we want to make 4 groups with the one available unit, we are forced to cut it into 4, and we have four groups that are each one a quarter of the unit available, thus 0,25.

Dividing 4 by 1,2:

With the **grouping** approach, the 1,2 fits into the 4 three times in its entirety, and one-third of it is enough to fill the remaining 0,4. Thus, the result is $3 + \frac{1}{3}$, or 3,33.

From the **partitioning** perspective, we are dividing 4 into 1,2 groups. This means that we are creating one group plus another group which is just 0,2 (or one-fifth) of the first one. The total is 6 fractional groups, 20% the size of a normal unitary group each. One fractional group is equal to $4/6$, or 0,66. Consequently, the result of the division (3,33) represents how many units there are in a unitary group, and the remaining 0,66 represents the content of the remaining 20% fraction of a unitary group.

Dividing 1 by 0,6:

Let's now analyze the trickiest case, a number divided by a fraction comprised between 0 and 1.

With the **grouping** approach, we think about how many times the 0,6 fits into the 1, or how many groups of size 0,6 fit into one.

With the **partitioning** approach, we try to understand how 1 unit can be divided into 0,6 groups, but what does it mean to create 0,6 groups? Does it even make sense to divide a number into a fraction of a group?

To understand how it is possible to divide 1 into 0,6 groups, remember that the result of a division, when interpreted through the partitioning approach, tells us the number of units of the dividend contained in each group unit. Normally, when the divisor is an integer, each one of the resulting groups is "complete".

For a divisor comprised between 0 and 1 however, the only resulting group is just a fraction of a unitary group, and the dividend (1 unit in our case) has to fit entirely into that fraction of a group. If the 1 has to fit entirely into this group, which is 60% of a normal or "complete" group unit, then the normal group must necessarily contain more than 1 unit.

Specifically, in order for a group that is 60% the size of a normal group to contain the number 1, the unitary normal group must contain a number X such that 60% of X is equal to 1 ($X = 1/0,6 = 1,66$). The 1 will be "squeezed" into a group which is a fraction of a unitary group, and we just have to find the normal filling of the unitary group.

In short, this is the meaning of the partitioning approach for fractional divisors between 0 and 1. The divisor is indicative of the number of groups, and the result of the division always tells us how many units there are in each entire group, even if the actual number of groups is less than 1.

Conclusion:

This paper has elucidated the duality between grouping and partitioning in division, particularly in the context of fractional divisors. Grouping focuses on how many groups the size of the divisor fits into the dividend, while partitioning emphasizes the size of each group formed. This framework allows for a deeper understanding of division, especially when dealing with fractions less than 1, by illustrating how the resulting group must encompass the entirety of the dividend.

By investigating how we conceptualize divisions, particularly with non-integer divisors, we are not just addressing a mathematical operation; we are engaging with the broader implications of how we understand numbers and their roles in reasoning, education, and philosophical thought.